

OBSERVATIONS OF MICROSCOPIC DAMAGE EVOLUTION IN OFF-AXIS PLYS UNDER FATIGUE LOADING

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ABSTRACT

In the present work properly designed glass/epoxy specimens with lay-up $[45_2/-45_2/0_2]_s$ were tested under uniaxial fatigue loading with the aim to observe damage evolution at the microscopic scale in the 45° ply. Microscope observations revealed that the first damage event was the initiation of micro-cracks in the matrix between the fibres. Macro-cracks then formed by coalescence of these micro-cracks and propagated along the fibres direction with the same mechanism. These experimental evidences confirm some assumptions at the basis of a recently developed criterion (Carraro and Quaresimin, 2014), which was indeed based on the idea that a macro-crack initiation under fatigue loading is driven by damage accumulation at the microscopic scale in the form of micro-cracks normal to the local maximum principal stress. The same specimens were tested in the presence of voids, revealing that the micro-scale damage mechanisms do not change in this condition.

1 INTRODUCTION

Multidirectional laminates are adopted in several structural applications, offering optimal specific strength and stiffness.

In-service conditions are usually characterised by uniaxial or multiaxial cyclic loads, which can lead to the initiation of multiple off-axis cracks and the degradation of the global stiffness. This behaviour is reported in several works in the literature for multidirectional laminates under uniaxial [1-7] or multiaxial loads [8,9].

As a consequence it is important to predict the initiation of cracks in the off-axis plies, with the final aim to define a procedure for estimating the progressive stiffness degradation of laminates. As the stress state in a ply of a laminate is in general multiaxial, even if the external load is uniaxial, as discussed in Refs. [10,11], a criterion for predicting the initiation of off-axis cracks must be capable of accounting for multiaxial stress states leading to a matrix-dominated behaviour.

In addition, a reliable crack initiation criterion of general validity should be based on the damage mechanisms leading to the onset of a crack.

The matrix-dominated fatigue behaviour of UD plies was characterised in the literature testing flat unidirectional off-axis laminates under uniaxial loading [12-16] and, by the present authors, tubular specimens under biaxial loading [11]. It was observed that fatigue failure, i.e. the specimen separation, occurred without any macroscopic evidence of damage evolution. In fact no macro-cracks (visible cracks) initiated before the final separation and no progressive stiffness decrease was measured during fatigue life, indicating the absence of a progressive damage at the macroscopic scale.

However, at the microscopic scale, damage must evolve from the early stages of fatigue life until it reaches a critical condition in correspondence of which a macro-crack initiate and unstably brings the UD specimen to the final failure. This is necessary to justify the sensitivity of composite off-axis plies to fatigue loading [17].

According to the authors' best knowledge, micro-scale observations of progressive damage evolution during cyclic loading are not available in the literature.

The present authors reported SEM images of the fracture surfaces of the 90° ply of glass/epoxy tubes subjected to combined tension-torsion cyclic loading [18]. The stress state in the 90° plies was characterised by the in plane shear stress σ_6 and the transverse stress σ_2 , which were combined

according to four values of their ratio $\lambda_{12} = \sigma_6/\sigma_2 = 0, 0.5, 1, 2$. Fracture surfaces were quite smooth for $\lambda_{12} = 0$ and 0.5 , whereas they were characterised by the wide presence of shear cusps in the matrix when shear stress contribution was higher ($\lambda_{12} = 1, 2$).

On these basis, it seems reasonable to assume that damage evolution at the microscopic scale, leading to the onset of a macro-crack, occurs in the form of initiation and subsequent coalescence of matrix micro-cracks, of which the results are the mentioned shear cusps observed after the complete separation. Accordingly, the present authors proposed a criterion to predict crack initiation, based on the assumption that the driving force for the initiation of such micro-cracks was the Local Maximum Principal Stress (LMPS) in the matrix, calculated by means of a multiscale strategy [19]. The criterion resulted in a good agreement with experimental results. However it was based on the assumption, however reasonable and derived after experimental observations, that the progressive damage at the micro-scale occurs by initiation and subsequent coalescence of micro-cracks in the matrix, thus causing the macro-crack initiation.

To confirm this hypothesis it would be helpful to observe the initiation of the micro-cracks by means of in-plane observations before the initiation of a macro-crack which corresponds indeed to the final failure if the specimen is unidirectional.

With this aim in the present work a dedicated specimen with lay-up $[45_2/-45_2/0_2]_s$ was designed and tested under uniaxial fatigue loading. The surface of the external 45° ply was accurately polished. The specimen was removed from the machine at regular cycles intervals and observed under an optical microscope, revealing the presence of micro-cracks between the fibres, before the initiation of macro-cracks. The through-the-width crack propagation phenomenon was also found to be driven by the same mechanism at the micro-scale.

Another objective of the present work is to understand the influence of voids on fatigue crack initiation. To this aim the same specimen configuration was analysed in the presence of voids, revealing that the damage mechanism is not affected, even if the micro-scale damage evolution process is strongly accelerated.

2 SPECIMEN DESIGN AND TESTING METHOD

Specimens with lay-up $[45_2/-45_2/0_2]_s$, schematically shown in Figure 1, were produced by liquid resin infusion using dry unidirectional glass fibres UT-E250 (250 g/m^2 , Gurit) and epoxy system EC157-W152LR (Elantas).

In the first panel the resin and the hardener were mixed and then degassed for 30 minutes to avoid the presence of air in the matrix.

Then a second panel was manufactured without degassing the matrix. This led to a lower infusion time but caused the presence of voids in the laminate, as shown later on.

The specimens were polished on the edges and on the top surface of the external $+45^\circ$ ply in order to make fibres and matrix clearly visible under a microscope. Tabs were then bonded at the ends of the specimens.

In this case the attention was focused on the external 45° plies, characterised by a biaxiality ratio $\lambda_{12} = 1.65$. This ensures a LMPS-driven damage evolution at the microscopic scale. The biaxiality ratio $\lambda_1 = \sigma_2/\sigma_1$ was estimated to be equal to 0.34 , which means that the longitudinal stress is of the same order of magnitude of the transverse and shear stresses. This leads to a matrix-dominated behaviour.

Specimens were tested under load control with $R = 0.05$ and a frequency of 3 Hz to avoid an excessive warming up. The global stress in the loading direction was chosen to be equal to 150 MPa , corresponding to a transverse stress of about 26 MPa in the external 45° ply.

The specimens were removed from the tensile machine with intervals of 500 cycles until reaching 6500 cycles.

Figure 1: Specimen configuration.

3 DAMAGE ANALYSIS IN THE ABSENCE OF VOIDS

As already mentioned, micro-cracks in the matrix, inclined with respect to the fibres, were revealed by the micrographs taken on the polished top surface of the 45° ply. Some of them are reported in Figure 2.

These micro-cracks represented the first event of damage in the off-axis layer, which preceded the initiation of macro-cracks.

Under this stress level micro-cracks were observed after 2000 cycles. Regions showing their presence were uniformly distributed along the specimen length and width, not only at the edges, as can be seen in Figure 2.

These observations confirm the assumption made by Carraro and Quaresimin [19] that under shear dominated loading conditions the progressive fatigue damage evolution at the microscopic scale is characterised by the initiation of multiple micro-cracks in the matrix, whose accumulation and coalescence lead to the formation of a macro-crack involving the entire ply thickness and propagating in the fibres direction.

After a macro-crack formed by coalescence of micro-cracks, the presence of surrounding layers made its propagation in the fibres direction stable.

It was observed that the micro-scale mechanism of crack propagation is similar to that for crack initiation.

In fact, in front of the tip of macro-cracks there was a process zone characterised by the initiation of multiple micro-cracks in the matrix, again inclined with respect to the fibres, as shown in Figure 3.

This mechanism is very similar to that observed by Carraro and co-authors for the fatigue propagation of bondline cracks in composite bonded joints under mixed mode I + II loading [20].

Also in that case, when the mode II contribution was predominant, the authors proved that the maximum principal stress within a process zone in the adhesive layer was the driving force for this kind of propagation mechanism [21].

Figure 2: Example of micro-cracks in the matrix, inclined with respect to the fibres direction; loading direction indicated by the arrows

Figure 3: Macro-crack propagation by means of micro-cracks initiation in a process zone; loading direction indicated by the arrows

4 DAMAGE ANALYSIS IN THE PRESENCE OF VOIDS

In the non degassed specimens several voids were observed both on the edges and on the top surface of the 45° ply, as shown in Figure 4. Most of voids are roughly circular in the edge view and elongated in the fibres direction.

Figure 4: Images of voids in the non degassed specimens

Also in the presence of voids the first damage event at the micro-scale was the onset of inclined micro-cracks between the fibres. Two scenarios were observed:

- micro-cracks initiated at the tips of voids sectioned by the polishing process;
- micro-cracks initiated above voids lying immediately beneath the surface.

Examples of these two scenarios are given in Figures 5 and 6, respectively.

Figure 5: Micro-cracks at the tip of a voids sectioned by the polishing process

Figure 6: Micro-cracks above a void beneath the surface

It can be concluded that the presence of voids does not change the mechanism leading to the initiation of a macro-crack. However it was observed that at the same stress level and number of cycles the number of regions showing the presence of micro-cracks was about 5 times higher in the presence of voids.

5 CONCLUSIONS

Specimens with lay-up $[45_2/-45_2/0_2]_s$ were produced by infusion. Two panels were manufactured with degassed and non degassed resin. The specimens were polished on the top surface of the 45° external ply, tested under uniaxial cyclic loading and periodically removed from the testing machine to be observed under a microscope.

The first event of damage in the 45° ply was the initiation of multiple micro-cracks in the matrix, inclined with respect to the fibres. The subsequent coalescence of these cracks led to the formation of macro-cracks propagating in the fibres direction with the same mechanism. In fact, in front of the tips of propagating macro-cracks a process zone was observed, characterised, again, by the presence of inclined micro-cracks in the matrix.

These observations provide a solid basis for a criterion recently developed by the authors for fatigue crack initiation.

In the presence of voids the damage mechanisms at the micro-scale were not affected by the voids themselves, the micro-cracks initiation and coalescence being just accelerated.

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